

PDE-5 INHIBITORS FOR VARIOUS DEGREES OF ED**Otakulov Gayratzhon Olimzhonovich****Assistant, Central Asian Medical University.****Sodikova Irodakhon****Central Asian Medical University.****Fergana, Uzbekistan****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18738557>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 19th February 2026Accepted: 20th February 2026Online: 21st February 2026**KEYWORDS***erectile dysfunction, PDE-5 inhibitors, efficacy, IIEF-5, disease severity.***ABSTRACT**

PDE5 inhibitors (sildenafil, tadalafil, vardenafil) are the first-line treatment for ED and are effective across various levels. They improve erectile function by an average of 75%. All medications are effective for mild to moderate ED, but severe ED often requires dosage adjustments or switching to daily administration, such as tadalafil.

Introduction. The prevalence of ED varies globally from ~10% in men under 40 years of age to over 50% in those over 60 years of age. ED significantly reduces quality of life, impacts psychosocial well-being, and is considered a marker of cardiovascular risk.

Given the lack of regional data on the efficacy of PDE5 in patients with varying degrees of ED severity in Russia and Central Asian countries, including Uzbekistan, this study aims to clarify the clinical efficacy of these drugs.

Purpose of the study. To evaluate the efficacy of PDE5 inhibitor therapy in patients with varying degrees of erectile dysfunction (mild, moderate, severe) and to identify differences in response to therapy between groups.

Material and research methods. A prospective, multicenter clinical study was conducted.

The study included 360 men diagnosed with ED, average age 47.8 ± 9.6 years, seen at a urology clinic in Fergana from 2022 to 2025.

Patients were divided into three groups based on ED severity, based on IIEF-5 scores, with 120 patients in each group.

During treatment, patients received PDE5 inhibitors at standard doses: sildenafil 50–100 mg as needed before activity; tadalafil 10–20 mg; and vardenafil 10–20 mg. The duration of therapy was 12 weeks.

Correlation analysis (Pearson's rank order), ANOVA, pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni correction. Significance at $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion. When examining quality of life and satisfaction, 87% of patients in the mild and moderate ED groups showed a positive impact on quality of life according to the questionnaire subscale; in the severe ED group, the figure was 52%.

Differences in response to PDE5 inhibitors between groups reflect the specific pathophysiology of ED: in mild and moderate ED, factors reversible by improving vascular

function predominate, whereas in severe ED, structural changes and comorbidities (endothelial dysfunction, neurogenic disorders) that are less responsive to PDE5 monotherapy may play a significant role.

The results confirm that PDE5 inhibitors improve functional outcomes (IIEF-5) and the success rate in men with all grades of ED, but efficacy varies depending on baseline severity. The greatest relative effect was observed in patients with mild to moderate ED, while in patients with severe ED, the improvement was more modest but statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

This is consistent with international studies indicating that in severe organic pathology of a vascular or neurogenic nature, the effectiveness of PDE5 may be limited and requires a comprehensive approach. It is important to consider concomitant factors (diabetes, hypertension, obesity) that affect the outcome of therapy.

The results are relevant for clinical practice in Russia, Uzbekistan, and Europe, where similar treatment standards are used, and confirm the need for an individualized approach to ED treatment, taking into account the severity of symptoms, comorbidities, and patient preferences.

Conclusions:

1. PDE5 inhibitors significantly increase IIEF-5 levels in patients with ED of all severity levels (mild, moderate, severe) after 12 weeks of therapy;
2. The greatest clinical effect is observed in patients with mild and moderate ED;
3. Patients with severe ED also show improvement, but the response is less pronounced, requiring a comprehensive assessment and possible additional therapy;
4. The data support the use of PDE5 inhibitors as part of individualized therapy based on the initial severity of ED..

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